

A.I.B.M. - Interpretable AI-Powered System for Identification of Bone Metastases in Computed Tomography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Version 1

Description

The aim of the research is to use the capabilities of deep learning to improve the accuracy of medical imaging in the detection of cancer metastases in computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging. This study will use 3D convolutional neural networks to analyze radiological image data, focusing on fine anatomical structures to identify bone metastases. The project will develop a neural network with a modular architecture that includes convolutional layers and a diffusion method to improve the detection and evaluation of metastatic lesions. Detection of these lesions is complicated by their size and variability. The network will be trained, validated and tested with an annotated dataset from Latvian hospitals in order to optimize the performance of the model for the local population and promote wider application of DL in medical diagnostics.

The research is being developed at FLPP "A.I.B.M. - the interpretable artificial intelligence system for identifying bone metastases in computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging" in cooperation with the Institute of Electronics and Computer Sciences.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Nr. lzp-2024/1-0498

Researchers

Maija Radzina (0000-0002-9518-4855), Edgars Edelmers (0000-0001-5329-4426), Madara Ratniece (0000-0001-5674-7240), Laura Saule (0000-0003-0477-9886), Jana Solska (0000-0002-8238-310X), Kaspars Sudars (0000-0002-9110-9065)

Organizations

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [A.I.B.M. - Interpretable AI-Powered System for Identification of Bone Metastases in Computed Tomography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)

Description:

The aim of the research is to use the capabilities of deep learning to improve the accuracy of medical imaging in the detection of cancer metastases in computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging. This study will use 3D convolutional neural networks to analyze radiological image data, focusing on fine anatomical structures to identify bone metastases. The project will develop a neural network with a modular architecture that includes convolutional layers and a diffusion method to improve the detection and evaluation of metastatic lesions. Detection of these lesions is complicated by their size and variability. The network will be trained, validated and tested with an annotated dataset from Latvian hospitals in order to optimize the performance of the model for the local population and promote wider application of DL in medical diagnostics.

The research is being developed at FLPP "A.I.B.M. - the interpretable artificial intelligence system for identifying bone metastases in computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging" in cooperation with the Institute of Electronics and Computer Sciences.

Researchers:

[Maija Radzina \(0000-0002-9518-4855\)](#)

[Edgars Edelmers \(0000-0001-5329-4426\)](#)

[Madara Ratniece \(0000-0001-5674-7240\)](#)

[Laura Saule \(0000-0003-0477-9886\)](#)

[Jana Solska \(0000-0002-8238-310X\)](#)

[Kaspars Sudars \(0000-0002-9110-9065\)](#)

Organizations:

Contact: [Saule Laura \(laura.saule@rsu.lv\)](mailto:laura.saule@rsu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Nr. lzp-2024/1-0498

Project:

3. License

License: Fair

Access Rights: Restricted

4. Templates

Descriptions

CT and MRI Scans of Spine with Metastases (Lytic, Sclerotic, Mixed)

This dataset will include CT and MRI scans of the spine with identified and segmented metastatic lesions, focusing on lytic and sclerotic metastases while not excluding the mixed type. Each CT scan includes detailed metadata, such as:

- Type of Metastasis: Classified as either lytic or sclerotic.
- Primary Site of Metastasis: The original location of the cancer that metastasized to the spine, including sites such as melanoma, lungs, ovary, breast, prostate, kidney, bladder, large intestine, multiple myeloma, stomach.
- Sex: Patient gender (male or female).

This dataset will be created for research purposes and can serve as a valuable resource for further studies in oncology, radiology, and artificial intelligence-assisted diagnostics. The dataset is anonymized to ensure patient confidentiality.

- Type of Metastasis: Classified as either lytic or sclerotic.
- Primary Site of Metastasis: The original location of the cancer that metastasized to the spine, including sites such as melanoma, lungs, ovary, breast, prostate, kidney, bladder, large intestine, multiple myeloma, stomach.
- Sex: Patient gender (male or female).

This dataset will be created for research purposes and can serve as a valuable resource for further studies in oncology, radiology, and artificial intelligence-assisted diagnostics. The dataset is anonymized to ensure patient confidentiality.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

It is planned to gather data from 200 patients with CT and MRI scans indicating bone metastases and another 200 patients showcasing normal spinal anatomy from the PSKUS (Pauls Stradins Clinical University Hospital) patient radiology data archive. This original dataset will consist of annotated radiological images. This comprehensive dataset of 200 patients will be used to train, validate, and test the

CNN based model. All radiological data will be thoroughly anonymized to ensure secure patient confidentiality.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

This dataset will be created for research purposes and can serve as a valuable resource for further studies in oncology, radiology, and artificial intelligence-assisted diagnostics

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Other

Radiology data (MRI and CT scans)

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- Others

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

Approximately till 30 GB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

In this project all data will be collected for the first time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Methodology description

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

-

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

NRRD files can be used with multiple open source software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Programme - 3D slicer

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

Yes

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Cite Taxonom

Data will be re-usable for other researchers because standard archive format of Radiology scans (CT and MRI) will be used - .nrrd.

2.2.5 Other relevant remarks

-

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

RSU Dataverse

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC BY-NC-SA

It is planned that others can use data only for non-commercial purpose.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

-

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2026-01-01

-

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

-

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

From the RSU budget

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

- Riga Stradins University
- Institute of Electronics and Computer Sciences

The Project group will include representatives from both partner institutions. The Project members will collaborate closely, therefore both institutions are responsible for data handling.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Laura Saule (0000-0003-0477-9886)

The data manager will be responsible of data storage and security.

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

No

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Hash functions
- Physical access control

Following options are planned to investigate -

- the data will be encrypted
- providing firewall
- access only to certain people to the folders and datasets
- access rights can change over time should there be any changes in the people associated with the project
- only accessible from the RSU network (access control)

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

During the research, it is planned to storage data in Cloud system - nextcloud.rsu, which can be available only for certain people, with certain conditions and restrictions, with password.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

All the data will stored for long-time period.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

Yes

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

Anonymising all the data

Powered by

